

Promoting Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights (SRHR) for Women and Girls in Nigeria

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Abstract

Sexual and Reproductive Health and Right (SRHR), as it affects women, has continued to be a topical issue in Nigeria. In many cases, Nigerian women and girls are exposed to a number of factors that have created an inconducive atmosphere for ensuring that their sexual and reproductive rights are protected and guaranteed. Issues such as early marriage, poverty, maternal mortality, rape, lack of access to SRHR services and information, continue to prevent these individuals from fully exercising their fundamental rights. Addressing these challenges requires concerted efforts from various stakeholders, including the government, civil society organizations, healthcare providers, and communities. Policies and programs aimed at promoting gender equality, ending child marriage, and preventing gender-based violence are crucial for safeguarding women and girls' SRHR. Improving access to SRH services, including education and information, and ensuring the availability of skilled healthcare providers are essential steps towards empowering women and girls to exercise their SRHR. Furthermore, community engagement and awareness-raising initiatives are essential for challenging harmful social norms and promoting positive attitudes towards women's rights and sexuality. By addressing the multifaceted barriers to SRHR in Nigeria, a more conducive environment can be created where women and girls can fully realize their sexual and reproductive health rights, leading to improved health outcomes and overall well-being.

Introduction

Ensuring Sexual and Reproductive Health Rights (SRHR) for women and girls is an area that has gained prominence globally. Spotlighted by the Programme of Action of the 1994 Cairo International Conference on Population and Development (ICPD), there has since been widespread recognition of the importance of safeguarding SRHR for women and girls. SRHR are interwoven with fundamental human rights, and emphasise the importance of ensuring women's autonomy and decision-making power over their own bodies and reproductive choices. Since the ICPD, SRHR have been integrated into various international agreements and frameworks, including the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [1]. This integration reflects the recognition that achieving sexual and reproductive health and rights is essential for achieving broader development goals such as gender equality, poverty reduction, and health for all [2]. In Nigeria, many women and girls lack access to essential information, sexual and reproductive health services, and agency

over their bodies, even as [3] reiterates that women's right to control all aspects of their health, in particular their own fertility, is basic to their empowerment. This disparity has far-reaching consequences, impacting not only their health but also their education, economic opportunities, and overall life trajectory. Despite Nigeria's efforts to lead the sub-region by signing initiatives to promote women's rights and investing in education, health, and reproductive services, implementation rates remain low [4]. This study examines the state of SRHR in Nigeria for women and girls and the possible way forward.

The Concept of Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights

Sexual and reproductive health (SRH) is defined by United Nations Fund for Population as a state of well-being, encompassing physical, mental and social, pertaining to the reproductive system, where individuals have the freedom to decide for themselves in all areas related to sex and the capability to reproduce. Safeguarding SRH, necessarily involves ensuring Sexual and Reproductive Rights, noted by [2]

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to include and focus on sexual pleasure and emotional sexual expression. As pointed out in the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action conference in 1995, women's sexual rights were established as having control over all decisions pertaining to their sexuality, without any form of coercion or discrimination. This includes rights that allow women and girls control over their bodies and decide for themselves all issues relating to child bearing, safe pregnancy and delivery, with adequate antenatal and postnatal care, as well as access to family planning counselling and a range of modern contraceptive methods [5].

Specifically, SRHR can be grouped into five main categories, as classified by [6].

1. The right to be reproductive, and sexual health as a component of overall life-long health.
2. The right to information on all matters relating to reproductive health.
3. The right to sexual and reproductive decision-making including, choice of marriage partners, family formation and determination of the number, timing and spacing of children, and the means to exercise those choices.
4. The right to equality and equity for women and men to make free and informed choices in all spheres of life, free from all forms of discrimination and violence.
5. The right to sexual and reproductive security, including freedom from sexual violence and coercion, and the right to privacy.

In Nigeria, women and girls still face a number of challenges despite efforts of the government and other stakeholders, due to prevailing sociocultural and institutional factors. Early marriage, for example, remains prevalent in many parts of Nigeria, depriving girls of their right to make informed decisions about their bodies and reproductive choices [7]. The high rate of maternal mortality underscores the challenges women face in accessing quality maternal health services, including antenatal care and skilled birth attendance [8]. Moreover, the pervasive issue of rape and sexual violence further exacerbates the violation of women's SRHR, perpetuating fear and insecurity in their daily lives. Additionally, the lack of access to comprehensive sexual and reproductive health (SRH) services and information limits women and girls' ability to make informed decisions about their health and well-being, including contraception, family planning, and sexually transmitted infections (STIs) prevention and treatment.

Significance of Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights

The significance of upholding SRHR for women and girls in Nigeria cannot be gainsaid. The accruing benefits for women and societal well-being are well recognised. Firstly, safeguarding SRHR can foster the achievement

of development goals. The Department for International Development [9] points out that maternal mortality can be prevented through improvement in access to well-integrated reproductive health services, including antenatal care and emergency obstetric care in cases of complications. Additionally, empowering women to avoid pregnancy too early in life, through family planning and the provision of modern contraception ensures they, not only have the ability to make more informed decisions about their sexual and reproductive lives, but reduces the risk of complication as well as maternal and child deaths. Also, better spacing of births reduces child mortality and improves maternal health. Sexual and reproductive health information and services are equally essential in the prevention of STDs such as HIV and AIDS [9].

Furthermore, the improvement of sexual and reproductive health is among the most cost-effective of all development investments, reaping personal, social and economic benefits [9]. [10] notes that, as stated by the Guttmacher Institute, for every \$1 invested in family planning programmes, up to \$6 can be saved by countries in cost associated with maternal and newborn health. These can make up resources that can be channelled into other parts of the economy such as towards improving infrastructure or education. Ensuring SRHR can also facilitate the achievement of gender equality and stabilise population growth and reduce poverty.

The recognition of the importance of SRHR among women has driven a number of government interventions, among them, the passage of the Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act, Administration of Criminal Justice Law, and the Anti-Discrimination Law in states such as Nasarawa and Benue. A number of health-related policies, as pointed out by [11], have also been introduced over the years including the National Health Policy and Strategy 1988 and 1998 (with the integrated health policy), Maternal and Child Health Policy (1994), National Adolescent Health Policy (1995) and the National Policy on the Elimination of Female Genital Mutilation (1998) [12]. As stated by [12], Nigeria's policy on reproductive health includes the following objectives.

1. Protection of reproductive rights through the creation of an enabling legal environment.
2. Protection of the rights of all people to make and act on decisions about their own reproductive health, free from coercion or violence, and based on full information within the framework of acceptable ethical standards.
3. Formulation and enforcement of legal instruments to support activities aimed at eliminating the practice of female genital mutilation and other forms of harmful practices such as gender-based violence, especially sexual violence and rape, through

intensified focus on public education and involvement of health care providers in the recognition and management of the problems.

4. Ensuring access of the public to scientifically proven preventive and curative reproductive health conditions including HIV/AIDS and protect them from unproven claims.
5. Removal of all forms of barriers that limit access to comprehensive, integrated and qualitative reproductive health care.
6. Adaptation of health facilities to the new concept of reproductive health as part of primary health care, through expansion and strengthening of outreach efforts at community level.

The policy, on paper, presents a potent way of achieving satisfactory level of SRHR for women in Nigeria, and the achievement of pertinent global and regional goals with regards to improved health, well-being, and overall quality of lives of Nigerians. The reality, however, paints a different picture. Despite the

laudable provisions of the policies, reproductive health care in the country is still far below international standards [11].

Challenges Associated with Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights in Nigeria

Poor Maternal Well-Being

The rate of maternal deaths in Nigeria remains one of the highest in the world, with the country accounting for 28.5 percent of global maternal mortality or 82,000 of estimated global maternal deaths in 2020 [13]. Nigeria’s maternity mortality rate is estimated to be at 1047 deaths per 100 000 live births [14]. This has been attributed to a number of factors, most of which are preventable. Comparing maternal mortality rate 2017 to 2020 (see figure 1) indicates how critical the problem in Nigeria is. Recent record of mortality rate in the country is only surpassed by Chad and South Sudan. In most cases, maternal rate showed a decline, in contrast to the situation in Nigeria which shows an increase.

Figure 1: Maternal Mortality Ratio per 100,000 live births in the African Region (2020 compared with 2017)
 Source: [14]

A critical factor in high maternal mortality rate is the lack of autonomy in maternal healthcare decisions, especially at the household level, where basic human rights are often undermined [15]. Power imbalances, cultural norms, and limited awareness can lead to family heads refusing medically necessary interventions, even when women themselves are willing to consent [16].

Violence against Women and Girls and Harmful Practices

Violence against women and girls remains a worrying reality in the country. [17] reports violence against women and girls as the most prevailing form of SRHR violations in Nigeria, with Lagos, Abuja Niger and Ogun

states recording the highest magnitudes of violations. A report by the National Population Commission (NPC) and the International Children Fund in 2018 indicated that 33% of women age 15-49 in Nigeria have experienced physical or sexual violence. Common forms include sexual harassment, physical assault, harmful traditional practices, emotional and psychological abuse, socio-economic exploitation and violence against non-combatant women in conflict situations [18].

Harmful practices such as Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) still prevail in many parts of the country, in different forms across different religions and cultures, affecting women and girls of various ages. [19] note the

commonly cited reason for FGM is curbing promiscuity among women. Such practices not only affect the societal positions of victims, but have been responsible for increasing the morbidity and mortality of women and girls from associated problems such as haemorrhage, shock, and infectious diseases including Hepatitis B and HIV/AIDS, as well as long-term

complications including recurrent urinary tract infections, infertility, sexual dysfunction, prolonged obstructed labour, chronic pelvic infection, vesico-vaginal and recto-vaginal fistulae (VVF and RVF). Even with the institution of a number of laws against the practice, FGM still persists in the country [20]

Figure 2: Incidence of FGM among Women and Girls in Nigeria across different Ages

Source: [21, 22]

Although studies done by [21-23] have shown the practice to be on the decrease, there still is a worrying trend in that 8.2% of girls between 0 and 14 years old and 15.1% of those between 15 and 49 are subjected to FGM as shown in figure 2.

Early Marriage

Female child marriage is a violation of the fundamental human rights of girls, and even though it has been on the decline globally in the past decade, the progress has been disparate with some regions still experiencing high rates [24]. In the North East and North West of Nigeria, it remains a prevalent practice, with approximately four in ten women marrying early [25]. [26] reports that 78% of girls in the northern region of Nigeria are married before the age of 18, 48% of girls are married by the age 15. With these figures, Nigeria has about 23 million child brides, the highest number in West Africa [21] (see figure 3), and one of the highest in the world. The prevalence of early marriage means that many girls are forced into marriage before they may be physically and emotionally ready to become wives and mothers. [25] report that child brides are at greater risk of experiencing poor health outcomes, having children at a younger age, having more children over their lifetime. This is in addition to having higher risk of intimate partner violence and possible lack of decision-making ability. Furthermore, child marriage contributes to lower educational attainment for girls, consequently leading to earning less in adulthood, and living in poverty. They added that the consequences of child marriage goes beyond affecting girls, but also their

children, households, communities, and the society as a whole.

Figure 3: Number of Girls and Women of all Ages Who Were First Married or in Union before Age 18

Source: [21]

Lack of Adequate Information on SRH

The common channels of SRH information according to [27], are the school environment, peers/friends, family, and social media. Faith-based organisations have also been known to provide sexual education to their members. They further stated that of all sources available, health facilities, parents, teachers, and youth friendly centers are considered appropriate sources of SRH information. However, utilising these outlets is not exactly popular amongst youths. This is because

Nigeria's cultural taboo surrounding sex and sexuality, as well as poor assurances of confidentiality, creates a silence that perpetuates a gap in sexual health education amongst young people despite premarital activity being common [28]. Thus, apart from the paucity of adequate information on sexual and reproductive health, there is the unwillingness to access available resources.

The Family Life and Health Education (FLHE) curriculum is an important tool used in Nigerian schools to promote sexual and reproductive health education. However, a 2019 cross-sectional study by [51] among school-age children and teachers in Nassarawa State revealed that while school teachers (44.1%) and mothers (28.4%) are the primary sources of FLHE information, only 4% of young people find this to be satisfactory.

This dearth of awareness about SRH may have serious outcomes. For instance, vulnerable youths may rely on their peers and uncontrolled media for information and support [29]. It also implies that women would not have access to contraceptive methods and will be subject to unplanned pregnancies, and sexually transmitted infections [30]

Lack of Access to, and Poor Attitude towards Sexual and Reproductive Healthcare Facilities

A hesitant attitude towards the use of sexual and reproductive healthcare services seem a crucial problem among women, especially adolescents. [31], from a study in North East Nigeria, note that utilisation of such facilities by adolescents has recorded low levels due to fear of being stigmatised, negative attitudes of health care providers and a lack of age-appropriate and adolescent-centred services. As pointed out by [32], and other studies [33-35], such reluctance to use formal healthcare services may lead to the use of alternative means of SRH care from unprofessional providers such as medicine vendors and traditional healers, and others self-medicate by purchasing drugs without prescription against the backdrop of antibiotic abuse and resistance. [32] add that lack of privacy, the negative attitude of health care providers, service cost and shortage of specialised services for adolescents were among reasons for not using such services.

Perception of care, and not actual quality of delivered care has also been observed to be an issue in a lot of cases preventing proper SRH in the country [36]. Cultural influences and personal prejudices have been found to be significant in preventing use of healthcare facilities by women. [37], for example, found that women preferred to carry out home deliveries even when a primary healthcare facility was located close to where they resided.

Poverty

Low socioeconomic status is a significant predictor of sexual and reproductive health violations among

women and girls [38]. Poverty often prevents access to education and information about SRHR leaving women and girls vulnerable to misinformation, harmful social norms, and associated health risks. [39] attribute a lack of financial autonomy as a major barrier preventing women and girls from accessing essential services like contraception and maternal care, particularly in remote communities where healthcare is seldom within reach. Nigeria's widespread impoverishment, with a significant portion of the population living on less than a dollar a day, has compelled many women to engage in transactional sex, which has in turn, contributed to the alarming spread of HIV infection and other STIs in the country [40]. Thus, poverty impacts women's physical and mental health, and addressing it is crucial to improving SRHR in Nigeria.

Strategies for Advancing Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights in Nigeria

Although some progress has been made in ensuring that women and girls in Nigeria can effectively access SRHR services, there is need for more awareness. The fact that this is recognised as a development goal emphasises its importance as a tool for achieving not just the well-being of women, but the progress of the society as a whole. Increasing access to proper information is crucial to achieving SRHR in the country. As emphasised by [2], ensuring SRHR depends on timely and comprehensive education that would, among other things, allow women and girls learn about their bodies and make informed decisions about their sexuality, and stand up against sexual harassment, exploitation and abuse. This also includes support for pregnancy as well as care and counselling in cases such as miscarriage, or for women suffering post-partum depression. A study carried out by [41] in Igbo-Eze North Local Government Area (LGA) of Enugu state in Nigeria, found that a significant number of women proved a better and positive attitude to reproductive health after intervention such as improved use of condoms to avoid concerns and risks associated with unprotected sex, HIV and STIs. Additionally, [42] established positive association between knowledge pertaining to SRH and the exhibition of protective sexual behaviour. This underscores the importance of intervention, in terms of provision of adequate information to ensure that Nigerian women are well equipped in safeguarding their sexual and reproductive health.

In a patriarchal society as Nigeria where inequalities are common, men must be carried along in discussions about contraception, family size, and reproductive health. Despite women being the primary target of family planning programs, it is often the men who make decisions about family size [3]. This is largely influenced by cultural, normative, social and economic factors, such as the need for husband's permission to access

services, service providers' insistence on spousal consent, and financial dependence on husbands [43]. In recognising the significant role men play in shaping reproductive choices, [44] recommended engaging family heads as well as other custodians of the society in reproductive, maternal and child health services and education.

Stringent and fully enforced laws are also needed in curbing violence against women and practices such as genital mutilation and early marriage. In the area of child marriage, there needs to be a modification of the Child Rights Act as well as enforced domestication of the Act in all states in the country [45]. Political commitment is necessary to make this a reality. As emphasised by [21], government intervention is needed in instituting child protection systems such as the social service workforce, as well as social programmes that increase the financial buoyancy of families in high-rate areas and increase girls' educational opportunities, as well as the provision of empowerment programmes and services that are adolescent-friendly and accessible to the poorest girls and their families [21].

Sierra Leone, like Nigeria, faced one of Africa's highest rates of child marriage. According to UNICEF, 30% of Sierra Leonean women aged 20 to 24 were first married or in a union between ages 15 and 18, with about 800,000 child brides in the country, half of whom were married before age 15. If current trends had continued unchecked, the UN projected that 27% of girls in Sierra Leone will be married before age 18 by 2030. However, on July 2, 2024, the President of Sierra Leone signed the Prohibition of Child Marriage Act into law, a landmark move banning child marriage and providing protections for victims, following significant advocacy by civil society groups [46]. Nigeria could enact similar legislation to support and promote girls' sexual and reproductive health and rights.

Furthermore, the promotion of access to, and use of healthcare services is also an important way of safeguarding SRH among women and girls in Nigeria. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), to protect SRHR, it is necessary to provide comprehensive and people-centred services that address its different components. Such services need to be supported by an enabling environment, quality health systems, and meaningful community engagement [47]. Researchers such as [32] highlight services centred on adolescent-centred sexual and reproductive healthcare, and willingness of adolescents to seek care in health facilities as the two major factors affecting sexual-related decisions such as the use of contraceptives. These facilities are essential in providing accurate SRH information, as well as the required testing and treatment services. Introducing digital services such as the use of telephone hotlines operated by trained

counsellors to provide SHR information to women and girls can eliminate cost, stigmatization and abuse of confidentiality, ensuring comprehensiveness and individuality [48]. Access to adequate care is also critical in preventing maternal mortality. [49] found in their study that 94% of maternal deaths were preventable. Leading factors causing deaths include inadequate qualified personnel, delay in seeking care, inadequate equipment, lack of ambulance transportation, and delay in referrals services, which could be avoided with availability of preventive measures and adequate care [50].

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the state of SRHR in Nigeria, with a focus on women and girls, aiming to promote their sexual and reproductive health and rights. Challenges such as inadequate maternal healthcare, gender-based violence, harmful practices like early marriage, limited information on sexual health, poor access to SRH facilities, and negative attitudes towards SRH services persist as significant barriers. Addressing these issues requires implementing robust policies that promote gender equality, women empowerment, child marriage elimination, and prevention of violence against women. Improving access to SRH services, expanding education, and ensuring the availability of skilled healthcare providers are critical for empowering women and girls to exercise their rights. To this end, the FLHE curriculum in Nigeria should be further reviewed to reflect both local values and global best practices, particularly with a focus on continuous professional development of teachers to deliver the curriculum effectively, and other impersonal sources like media outreach programs should be leveraged. With just 6 years left to achieve the UN's 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, time is of the essence, and Nigeria must adopt decisive measures to address the SRHR challenges faced by women and girls. In line with actions taken by Sierra Leone, Nigeria should consider passing legislation to abolish child marriage to substantially protect girls' rights. Additionally, community engagement and awareness campaigns are vital for challenging harmful social norms and promoting positive attitudes towards women's health and rights. The government at all levels must also increase budgetary allocations for SRH services, with sustainable implementation and evaluation. More women and youth friendly SRH facilities should be erected, either as standalones or integrated into health centers. Through these combined efforts, Nigeria can make meaningful progress in advancing SRHR for women and girls.

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